

- 20190510_OO_student1_CODE.txt
- 20190510_OO_student1_transcript0...
- 20190510_OO_student2_CODE.txt
- 20190510_OO_student2_Transcript0...
- 20190510_OO_student13_CODE.txt
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- 20190514_OO_student3_CODE.txt
- 20190514_OO_student3_Transcript0...
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- 20190514_OO_student5_CODE.txt
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- 20190517_OO_student6_CODE.txt
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- 20190517_OO_student7_CODE.txt
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- 20190517_OO_student8_CODE.txt
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1
2 [00:00:00]
3
4 [BEGIN TASK 34A]
5 R: Ok, so you may not compile. The first question I wanna ask you, or maybe you can read it yourself.
6 S: Describe the purpose of this code, and if the code was written in a function, give a proper name for the function.
7 R: So I don't want you to tell me what, first read it, tell me, think out loud, tell me what you're thinking when you read
  it, what do you see...
8 S: Ok, so it has a list which would probably be a parameter, if it was a function, then it takes the first value and then
  looks for each of the values, if the value's smaller than the current... It determines the minimum of the list. Ehm...
  yeah, and if the value that we're currently looking at is smaller than the one that we have stored so far, it replaces it.
  So this is basically a function that determines the minimum of the rainValues list, so if it would be placed in a function,
  it would be something like intmain and would take an integer array as an argument instead of a hard coded one, and would
  return it instead of print.
9 [END TASK 34A]
10 [BEGIN DISCUSS TASK 34A]
11 R: Perfect. Yeah, the reason why I asked you if it would be placed in a function, because I don't want, so people would
  tell me, well the printed becomes the value of... And I don't want you to read to me what is said but exactly, perfect, you
  said it's the minimum of the list. Awesome. Ok, I'd like you to answer these three questions about it.
12
13 [00:01:21]
14
15 R: How difficult did you find the programme code while you were reading, did you, was it very difficult to understand what
  the code did?
16 S: Well, it's a pretty standard function, so, ehm... In this case not really difficult code. It also doesn't use very
  difficult concepts. It's sort of, what, an enhanced for-loop over the array and an if-statement, so it's also not really
  complex code, so it also...
17 R: You called it an enhanced for-loop, why do you call it an enhanced for-loop?
18 S: An enhanced for-loop, because it goes over the array, and a normal for-loop is the one with, in i is zero, and this, we
  learned that in object-orientation and [?]. And ehm, the instructions, well, was, I did know what I had to do.
19
20 [END DISCUSS TASK 34A]
21 [00:02:05]
22 [BEGIN TASK 34B]
23
24 R: Ok, perfect. Same type of question but a little bit different.
25 S: Ok. Rainvalue... Ok, it's the same thing... Int i equals zero, then over the length, so this also goes over the entire
  array, so i is [not?] a subscript into the rainValues, ok if it's greater than the current one, and then increment i, this
  is the while equivalent to a normal for-loop, and it's the maximum function of the rainvalues.
26 [END TASK 34B]
27
28 [BEGIN TASK 34C]
29 R: All right, perfect. You're probably gonna laugh when you see this one, or recognize it at least.
30 S: Ok, it... It counts how many values in there are zero, so since it's rainvalues, basically how many days there were
  where it didn't rain. And, yeah, it's just a standard for-loop over the entire array, and, checks whether they're zero.
31 R: OK.
32 [END TASK 34C]
33
34
35 [00:06:56]
36
37 R: Now I'm gonna ask you to type some code in. So, maybe you wanna read...
38 [00:07:00]
39
40 R: Ok. Can I ask you something? Can you do, because you told me that you could also do two iterations? Could you write the
  code, how you would write it for two iterations? So if you would do it with a, determine first the max?
41
42 [00:13:02]
43
44 S: Well, ehm... Determining the max... Should be, the arrays has a .max function, like, in that case I could just use the...
45 R: And if it doesn't, could you determine it without using the max function?
46
47 [BEGIN TASK 81 (B)]
48 [00:13:20]
49
50 S: Well, I could also in that case, yeah I would need to go over the array myself, because, since I don't have a given
  library function... Ehm... I could actually still need the a temporary variable outside to keep my count max, so here's my
  count max... again -1, to do, to say if I value that can actually happen, then this is basically the code in, ehm, 34, in
  one of the, 34b, had the same code. I'm actually doing it with an enhanced for-loop, so, yeah. If elem is greater than
  max... max is elem... I also know there's no need for the braces but I always add the braces, even if it's just a single-
  line statement, because I feel like it makes the structure clearer. So that, it just helps me personally to understand what
  is inside the if-statement. And then after that pass [iteration over the array] maximum has the highest value that is in
  the array, and then, int count zero... And then for... print elem of rainvalues... Ehm... if elem is the same as maximum,
  then increment the count. So, basically this and then print out, and then of course we turn the count [increment the
  count]. Ehm... Yeah, so this basically would be the same thing except it passes over the array once to determine the
  maximum, and then once to see how many elements are actually equal to the maximum.
51 [END TASK 81 (B)]
52 [00:15:36]
53 [BEGIN DISCUSS TASK 81 (B)]
54 R: Ok. And if I would ask you to answer these questions for the way that you solved it now, if you look at your program
  code...
55 S: Oh yeah, ok, that's simple but. Ehm... Ok, as it turns out I actually thought it would be easier if I split it up into
  two loops, but I now that I look at it, both, it seems like the two loops just make it more complex as well because now you
  have to think, why do you equate over it twice and not just once. But now I feel like it's much, actually easier to print
  one way, but it's kinda hard to say, because I obviously understand what happens here. So it's hard for me to judge how
  someone on the outside basically would see it. I'd say... I would say though, it's a bit easier because you can write
  methods as a standard for determining the maximum and in the real one you would use the library function, so max, it would
  make it even clearer what is going on. Although you should pay attention not to put the arrays.max in the condition here
  because that would go over the entire array each time. Come to think of it, like I can imagine that someone would do that,
  if the element is equal to the maximum, then it would run for each time. Hmm.. Well, it's no more complex, it's still just
  for and if-statements, and yeah.
56 R: Ok. And would you still organise it in the same place? Second solution...?
57 S: The second solution I would actually put up here, between these two. I feel like... yeah, I feel like it would be a bit
  easier to read actually.
58 R: Easier to read than the conditional...
59 S: 34c.
60 R: Yeah because, yeah, you're using this one, so it's only a little bit more difficult than the standard for.
61 S: Yeah because this just returns minimum and this now determines maximum and something else. So it's more difficult.
62 R: Yeah, because it determines something else in one case the count, and the other that.
63 S: And I'm just thinking what happens if value, if you give it an empty array. Because that's like one of the edge cases
  that you can have. I guess.. ehm.. yeah, count is just gonna be easier still then, in either case. which makes sense cause

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You: S1: construct familiarity
Jan 10, 2024 10:38 AM • Edit
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You: S6 while harder/error prone than for
Jan 10, 2024 10:38 AM • Edit
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You: S6 while harder/error prone than for
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You: O4NEG recalls familiar plan
Jan 10, 2024 9:33 AM • Edit
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You: S24 # tasks subsequent
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You: S24 # tasks subsequent
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an empty array, the maximum never fell. The most sensible thing you can return anyways.

64 [END DISCUSS TASK 81 (B)]
65 [00:18:06]
66
67 R: Ok, perfect, thank you. Ehm... Then I have another task for you.
68 [00:18:10]
69 [BEGIN TASK 83]
70 S: Ok. [reads text] the index of the first rainy day and the last rainy day... If there are no rainy days... Ok, so the first rainy day is just one where the value is not zero, I guess, and ok, the first rainy day until the last rainy day... Hm.. Well I can't use an enhanced for-loop at least, because I need the index actually, so I need a normal for-loop... And then, well, the thing is the last rainy day, it would probably be easiest to find it if I go like, backwards. Yeah, I think it would be easiest to just, if I go backwards over the array. Like I start once at the front and go forward and once at the end and go backwards. It's probably not the fastest way but else I would need the variable to keep track of the state, like whether I'm in a rainy section or not, I need to go through the entire array... Well actually it's still faster if I go forwards once and backwards one other time. Because else I need to go to the end to find the last element. So... and if there are no rainy days, print error message. Ok. In that case, again... So first off, I'm gonna declare two variables for the... For the first day and for the last day, and I'm gonna initialize both to minus one. Ehm... So I know, because I'm supposed to give an error message if there is no last day, if there is no rainy day, and if I see, if I go through the first for-loop and I see that the index is still minus one, because there was no rainy day, then I can print out the error message. Actually I don't need to search for the last one in that case. So first off go over it, now with a normal for-loop because I need to store the index, i is less than rainValues.length... Ehm, i++, And, ehm... Well, we don't care if it's raining or not... Well, we don't care much if it rains, so if rainValues[i] is greater than zero... Then set first day to i and break. Because, when we find the first day and if it kept iterating on it would find the other rainy days as well, so this stops the for-loop. You could also do this and I imagine our professor would prefer that way with a variable that says finished or not, and then sets it true, but I personally prefer breaking out of a loop. Guess it's a difference of style. Then the error message... If first day is still minus one, then ehm... print an error message. So system.out.println... Ehm, an error message, so system.err... or if this was a function I would turn exception, because for subfunction it would not be a good style to ehm... just print something to a console, when an error occurs, so error not exception. In this case, system.out.println... Ehm... there are no rainy days... Ehm, and actually return, which in this case quits the programme, but also in subfunction it would make sure that, well, in the subfunction of an exception it doesn't matter, but this case it makes sure that doesn't also try to go backwards through the entire array, because we already know there is no rainy day. And now I'm just going to copy this, cause, well a part of it stays the same, except that i is now rainValues.length, minus one, i is greater or equal to zero and i is minus minus, which is a loop that goes backwards over the entire array. And then rainValues is i and in this case, ehm, last day. Ok, and then we... print... And since it's, I got a format here, which has the numbers in the middle, I'm actually gonna use print f, with ehm, first day and last day as arguments, I could also do string plus integer, because it converts it automatically, but this is pretty much why formattings were invented, and adding a string to an integer is something that not all languages handle quite well, actually Java is fine, Java does it the same way, yeah. And index of...
71 R: Yeah I was just about to say, you can cut-paste if you want...
72 S: Except of course we're replacing these with a percentage d... And I think, yeah this is... and because this is quite long, I'm gonna push these two to the next line, so you can still see what it's effectively printing out. So it's now the content of the message, even if you don't see the entire formatting, so yeah, this...
73 [END TASK 83]
74 [00:24:34]
75 [BEGIN DISCUSS TASK 83]
76
77 R: Ok, excellent. Then have a look at your code, and the task of the program code...
78 S: Well I'd say, especially what people, what also is the most complex part here is the ehm, the reversed for-loop because that, like I think that would be the most difficult thing, ehm... what it does I imagine is pretty clear, because ehm, this is a standard for-loop and the variable names, I'd say also give you a certain amount of guidance. Like, what first day stores, if you set it equal to the index variable it's pretty obvious, if you don't know what it's supposed to do, and, yeah, I mean, this one documents itself with what the problem is, so this already tells us when is this if given, so I imagine the most difficult part of this would be the backwards form.
79 R: Yeah, because you have a forward for-loop and a backwards, you say the backwards is more trickier than the first.
80 S: Yeah, it's trickier to read, because you need to make sure that you both don't get, use rainValues.length as an index and that you also remember to use, to check the first element, for example if only the first day is a rainy day, and I've typed i greater zero, then it wouldn't work properly. So with a backwards loop, it's not as nice to write, because the index starts at zero, not one. So I'd say this is more complex than the ones before, also more complex definitions and concepts than the one before.
81 R: What makes it...?
82 S: Mainly the backwards for-loop I imagine, like that's gonna be the biggest problem in understanding. I don't feel like this is also gonna be the example the next to students to check what it does. And yeah, the task was a bit more difficult to understand than the previous one, I'd say, not understand, but it was a more complex task than the previous ones.
83
84 [00:26:41]
85
86 R: Ok, but this is about, did you know what I was asking, did you know what you had to do...
87 S: Yeah, I knew what I had to do, but it's a more difficult task than the ones before.
88 R: Ok, and what made it more difficult?
89 S: Well for one, that we had to actually check whether it's a sensible input, because we had to check whether there are any rainy days, which otherwise, if it didn't explicitly say this, I imagine a lot of programs would happily print out index of first rainy day minus one, index of last rainy day minus one. And yeah, that we actually have to keep track of the indices, because we need them, we can't use an enhanced for-loop for this. Ehm... Since we aren't allowed to use library functions in this one, since I'm not allowed to use a library function, that doesn't matter typically, but I would also think about doing is, ehm, do a forwards for-loop for the second one as well, but use arrays of reverse, because that both tells you what it does and also is easier to read, but at the same time, arrays of reverse has a pretty bad runtime, O of n I think, expect, so it might also slow the programme down significantly, if you have more than eight rain values.
90 R: Because, when you started off, you wanted to use a function, what was the max, to find the max of a list I think. Would that have made it easier for you?
91 S: Not so much for me, the max function is easy enough to write, but it makes it easier for someone to read, because then they don't have to think, what does the for-loop do, they just see ok, arrays.max, obviously that finds the max element in the array.
92 R: So writing is not that hard but it makes it easier, yeah...
93 S: It makes it easier to write because it states the intention, yeah. I could've also added a comment to first find the maximum and then a second comment, now check how many elements are equal to this maximum. So that is something, so I would need to comment it because it isn't a function.
94
95 [00:28:49]
96
97 R: Ok, and how can we order it? Where would you place it?
98 S: Ehm... I would actually place this one, maybe because the forward and the backwards loop, at the bottom of the list so far. So I'd say this is the most complex one so far. But I also see that there's still some left on the scoreboard.
99 R: Yeah, no, we're not gonna do all of them. Don't worry, I'm not gonna keep you here that long.
100 S: Oh, I don't have anything else to do today, so...
101
102 [00:29:24]
103
104 R: Ok, ehm... One or two more questions.
105
106 [BEGIN TASK 90 (B)]
107 [00:34:49]
108 R: You wanna change it to a for-loop? Then you just copy it and do a new one.
109 S: [copy-past code] Ehm... On the outer for-loop it still stays the same, but ehm... Int i is zero, i is less than rain amount, for... And then I can get rid of this one... Yeah. So that should do the same thing, we can't compile because it does the same plus twice, so it's gonna complain about that, but ehm... yeah.

Resolve Reply

You: O6 considers/knows construct - plan combo
Jan 10, 2024 9:36 AM • Edit
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You: O9 considers efficiency
Jan 10, 2024 9:37 AM • Edit
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You: NOT 03: lacking terminate plan
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You: O9 considers efficiency
Jan 10, 2024 9:40 AM • Edit
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Resolve Reply

You: S12 difficulty tweaking plan
Jan 10, 2024 9:42 AM • Edit
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You: S11 boundary values or termination conditions
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You: S10 tweaking construct (parameters)
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You: S24 # tasks subsequent
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You: S20 #variables to think about
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You: O9 considers efficiency
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110 [00:33:19]
111 [END TASK 90 (B)]
112 [BEGIN DISCUSS TASK 90 (B)]
113
114 R: And eh, why would you prefer one above the other?
115 S: I don't really... The thing is just, this makes use of the fact that integers are copied by value, that integers are not objects, so like, can't be copied with reference. **so it keeps in another variable**, but then again an integer is not really that bad, and this one would also for example work if you didn't have rainvalues as simple integers, but for example integer, actually integer objects would just cost and not run the loop, but for example if you had another object type, where you don't have a simple int, but an object that actually, ehm, like, is passed with reference, then this one would then, importing this one would then change the original object, which in a function is generally not something I'd want to do. Like I don't want the function to just, if this is not its purpose, then I don't want a function to alter any of its objects.
116 R: And first you said, oh the while, I prefer the while, I use the while instead of a for, because it uses less variables, what's your, why would you like to use less variables?
117 S: Ehm... I guess it's because I've been reading for the past couple days, ehm, a guide to programming. It's somewhat older, it's actually older than the new C standards, so it's from '88 I think, but it was a recommendation by Peter Schwabe for his "hacking in C" course and I've been reading through it, and he advised to using less variables where you can, which obviously because it was '88 and storage space was way rarer than it is now, but I just remembered that, and additional integers is not going to really make a difference, in the grand scheme of things, or in the memory consumption. Like, it's not gonna be, it's gonna be a bit less performing, but at the same time, it's, the performance I lose by waiting for I/O's is probably far bigger than any I lose by making a new integer.
118
119
120 [00:40:03]
121 [CONT. DISCUSS TASK 90 (B)]
122 S: **And with the double for-loop, well, it's, it's a bit less complex, I'd say, like you can easier see what is going on, obviously string.repeat or something would still be nice, they added that in Java 10 actually, strings since Java 10 had a repeat method, finally, ehm, but ehm, yeah, it's a little bit less complex, but in terms of the structure, it's really no more complex.**
123 R: Because you say you can immediately see what is being done.
124 S: Yeah, honestly the high values on this scale I'd reserve for anything that's like, with recursive objects or something, that would be complex, ehm, things, but obviously, we also don't have the time for that.
125
126 [00:41:58]
127
128 R: Ok, and where would you order it...
129 S: I'd actually put it above those...
130 R: Because?
131 S: **Because with a double for-loop I feel like it's easier to read than with a while-loop. Like, a while-loop in general is something that also from when other people have looked at my code they always are pretty, well, that while-loops are something that most people don't really see a lot. Like, you don't see while-loops a lot because for-loops are typically always a better solution. And the few cases where while-loops are used, is something like while there is another character input or something, but in Java you don't do input yourself, you have a function to get, like you have a scanner to get integers, you don't need to write it yourself. So you don't see it that much.**
132
133 [END DISCUSS TASK 90 (B)]
134
135
136 R: Ok, excellent. Then I have one more question for you. Merging two lists.
137
138 [BEGIN TASK 88 (B)]
139 [00:50:07]
140 **So what I mean is... dot length... i++, that's also something I imagine some people would miss, that it actually increments by two because you use the same for and i equals zero, or is less than the length, ok, and they wouldn't notice that it's i+ equals two instead of i++. And obviously with i++ the whole logic doesn't make sense.**
141 R: And that depends on the array you choose to iterate over.
142 S: Yeah, the array I iterate over... shift is a really odd key, I'm used to being like...
143 R: You say the German keyboard is different?
144 S: Yeah, it's ehm... we obviously have umlaut on these three keys, but then we have on this one, we have plus and above it a star.
145 R: Ok.
146 S: So ehm, yeah, I always want it here, but it's actually up there. For the process it's not as bad, because it's still nearby
147 R: But the star's really far, yeah.
148 S: So, and then don't divide by two.
149 [END TASK 88 (B)]
150 [00:51:16]
151 [BEGIN DISCUSS TASK 88 (B)]
152 S: This is basically if you did it, if you iterate it over the other one, so two times i and then two times i plus one. Which turns out to be zero and one for the first one, then two and three for the next one, ehm... I'm not sure, it doesn't require you to know that it's integer division, someone might think if he doesn't know that this always rounds off, then actually returns a floating value, especially with someone that's used to Javascript or Python, where types aren't as strict as, an understatement, there are no types, effectively, where this would give exceptions, because floating point indices, so ehm..
153 R: Yeah in Python it would just round it off as well.
154 S: Yeah well, actually no, would it? I think no, in Python floor division is double slash. Ehm, single.. Ehm, I'm not sure... I'd have to try that out actually.
155
156 [00:57:47]
157
158 [CONT DISCUSS TASK 88 (B)]
159 R: Yeah, but the harder task shows that it's a more complex... Ok, and for the way that you attempted it the second time? Is the code harder?
160 S: Well, I'd say it's a bit easier, you still need to check, **you still might need to try with the, two times i and two times i plus one**, but now you only increment i by one each time, and you also don't divide so you don't need to pay attention to floor division so it takes out basically the two things that you could stumble over, when trying to understand this, and ehm, when I try to understand it at a later time as well, ehm.. So those are the two tracks basically, in here now that no longer exists so here it is a good bit easier. And well, as far as concepts and definitions go it doesn't make all too much of a difference. Like it's still the same with the for-loop and the two compound arrays.
161 [CONT DISCUSS TASK 88 (B)]
162 R: Ok. For the top one..
163 S: For the top one... I'd say it's a number four, but at the same time with the indices, I'd say it's still probably easier to read than this one, with the expanded for-loop (refers to a normal for loop- 34c) but not really by much, I'd say.
164 R: Ok, and the expanded, yeah, because it uses the expanded, and what makes it easier than the while, what makes it easier than this one?
165 S: Easier to read mainly, because it, because in this one you really, actually it's the same problem, you would need to go through a couple of iterations of the loop to realise what it actually is doing, **in this case that it's just the standard for-loop and in this case that it, like, does both arrays at the same time.**
166 R: Ok.
167 S: If I think about it with arrayLists I could have used iterators which would've made it pretty much obvious because then I could have added with .next and then I think with arrayLists and iterators it would have been even easier to ehm, see what is going on because that way it would have actually even had methods with names that you can use, as opposed to just operators and stuff.
168 R: Ok, and so this one, you're talking about the top, right? The merged iterator... Ok I'm going to take a picture of
+***

You: S20 #variables to think about
Jan 10, 2024 9:46 AM • Edit
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You: S9 nested loops easy
Jan 10, 2024 9:47 AM • Edit
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Resolve Reply

You: S6 WHILE harder/dispersed/error prone than FOR
Jan 10, 2024 9:47 AM • Edit
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Resolve Reply

You: S1 construct familiarity
Jan 10, 2024 9:48 AM • Edit
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Resolve Reply

You: S10 tweaking construct (parameters)
Jan 10, 2024 9:49 AM • Edit
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You: S10 tweaking construct (parameters)
Jan 10, 2024 9:53 AM • Edit
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Resolve Reply

You: S10 tweaking construct (parameters)
Jan 10, 2024 9:52 AM • Edit
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Resolve Reply

169
170 [END DISCUSS TASK 88 (B)]
171 S: Oh, you said that was the last one, right?
172
173
174 [01:02:22]
175 [BEGIN TASK 89]
176 R: Well if you want to, do you want to do it?
177 S: I was gonna say... It's not gonna take long, just a second... and i equals zero... never mind that, I can use an enhanced for-loop, ehm... int rainValue of rainValues, ehm... int amount is zero, and one named sum is zero, because like, I need to keep track of the amount of values I have and the one in sum cause I not, I can't use array.length because this one would ehm, then also divide by eight so I need to keep track of both the amount and that, so ehm... If rainValue is greater than zero, and it don't actually give you every course, so yeah... I don't need an else here because if it's less than zero we just skip over that element, but if the rain value is bigger than the amount++ and runningSum+ equals rain value... so yeah. And then I'd say... and then I'm just gonna write it down. Ehm... for the time being... return ehm... and now there's the tricky thing, because it might be that all of them are negative. Like, the entire array only has negative values, or zero, and that way if amount would still be zero, so I need to check that. Amount is zero... if so return zero, because that's the best you can give for an average of an empty array. Else runningSum over amount... So in this case the time you operate it because yeah, over an empty array, technically the average is meaningless but still zero is the best I can give. Actually maybe negative values if I, well there is none, but yeah.

178 [BEGIN DISCUSS TASK 89]
179 R: And how would you find your program code now?
180 S: Not all too complex, ehm... it's a normal for-loop with an if-statement in it, basically no worse than what we've seen, which one was it actually, what we've seen here for the 34a, which I actually stored at the very top, so... It's not really a complex programme, and the only thing that I could imagine someone needs to take a second look at is the amount, also I just remembered something else, which is a problem, ehm... So I have to fix it... Ehm, double runningSum because else the ehm... runningSum over amount might, would be rounded off and we don't want that for an average. It shouldn't be rounded off. If we use a round-off average, we can get that, but it, you should cast it to int himself.

181 [01:06:08]
182 [END TASK 89]
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184 [BEGIN DISCUSS TASK 89]
185 R: And so you're saying, yeah the construct is just as much, yeah, but there's, because in 34a you're saying we have a for-loop, a for each and an if in it. And here you say, you have one variable more
186 S: Yeah I put another variable, that's not... I think necessarily, but ehm... I don't think, again, I feel like the variable names already say what is meant. Like, if the rainValues are greater than zero, the amount increments by one. Then obviously it's increment, then it means that the amount of days where the rainValue was greater than zero. And which reminds me, greater than or equal to zero [types > into >=], because it's set on non-negative values. So, ehm, yeah. That's the thing, if you don't have, ehm, you can't test it. You miss this, but eh, yeah.

187 R: And how about your return statement?
188 S: What do you mean? Yeah, or print, I don't know, this won't compile, because it's a void function but returns, but ehm... typically this would be a subfunction, so you would return.
189 R: Ok, because you say it's not, can you say where you would place it?
190 S: Place it... I think the fact that you have these variables that you need to check what they're doing, would make it a bit more complex than actually ehm... this one. At the same time I don't think really, it's not really complex program, I guess...
191 R: What makes it harder than that one?
192 S: Well, harder than that one, mainly the fact that it takes the two variables it maintains and increments both of them at the same time. Ehm... and harder than this one, also plus the terminal statement, like, I feel like this is a bit complex for a terminal statement because an if-statement it would be overkill, like, if amount zero return zero else return runningSum amount. I feel like that would be too much, but at the same time you could do it, some people really don't like this return really [refers to if then else in one line of return statement] but ehm, some of our teachers don't like this return, ehm, some say it's fine for stuff like this, again it's more manner of taste really, not really a matter of...
193 R: And it's easier than the amount of days maximum, that was you first determined the maximum and then count how many days there is?
194 S: I'd say it's easier than that because it doesn't have, because that also had two variables to maintain but it had a second, like it had an if-else, and you actually reset the value sometimes, but with this, you always just counted up. And again, I'm not a good judge on how complex my programme are. I know that I've worked in code where I thought that's pretty easy to understand, where I've had feedback from my teaching assistants which was that it's really hard to understand, so I'm not the best judge in that.

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197 [01:09:27]
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199 R: No, but I really like the way that you're talking me through it. You're giving me a lot of information. Excellent. [explains about another programme for students] Oh, can you put the average, I forgot that one.
200 S: Well, the average of some non-negative values... I want to say it's a really easy one, but at the same time I forgot that it's a non-negative, and that it's positive values, so I'm, can't really say it's... So I'd say this is a fairly easy task. Obviously at the same time I'm currently also thinking in the back of my head about our current assignment which is a pattern of a formula evaluation, and compared to that these are all very easy. But to be fair that's also university level, almost last exercise.
201 R: And second course, right.
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203 S: Well, first one for object orientation, but yeah.
204 R: But you've seen lists before.
205 S: Yeah, this would all be function and programming and stuff, we didn't use objects that didn't use helper methods, because it was, I don't know where that could have anywhere, if anything with the asterisk I might have used an helper method for each row, like right number of, right this many asterisk function, but even that's not really necessary. It's a very small function, and it's not a task that you typically need to do, if anything a repeat function would be nice, but ehm... So it's not all too complex the code and also not really complex definitions, just for and if. So I'd also say not really complex.

206 [END DISCUSS TASK 89]
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208 R: Ok, excellent, thank you very much.
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You: O10 minor forget&recall
Jan 10, 2024 9:57 AM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: S20 #variables to think about
Jan 10, 2024 9:57 AM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: S13 integrating multiple plans/merging harder
Jan 10, 2024 9:58 AM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: S18 nested conditional hard (harder than nested loop)
Jan 10, 2024 9:59 AM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

